

The 21st–Century Visitor Center Renaissance

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The new mural on the concrete 4m "donut" in the Visitor Center parking lot.

The Visitor Center is the public's window to the people, facilities, science, and accomplishments of Kitt Peak National Observatory (KPNO) and has been since 1964. It is the public face of the observatory and a dynamic public portal, showcasing the history, unique research facilities, and new capabilities of KPNO, a Program of NSF's NOIRLab.

The Kitt Peak Visitor Center has completed a four-year-long, much-needed renaissance that we hope will lead to an even more dramatic transformation in the near future. The timing of the improvements coincided nicely with recent multimillion dollar investments at three scientific workhorse facilities on Kitt Peak: the KPNO 2.1-meter Telescope, the WIYN 3.5-meter Telescope, and the Nicholas U. Mayall 4-meter Telescope.

The visitor program is not funded by any federal agency or observatory, so the Visitor Center relies entirely upon outside assistance for any improvements or new exhibits

and from program and gift shop income to operate on a daily basis. We were able to undertake transformations to the Visitor Center interior and several exterior areas and bring online a new dual-purpose observatory, all at a very low cost. We have utilized donations to our Visitor Center Telescope Fund, a one-time allocation of funds from the National Optical Astronomy Observatory, funding from the SARA observatory consortium, and donations made as memorial gifts by two families. The recently completed improvements demonstrate the impact that modest-scale donations can make at the Visitor Center.

We chose to put these investments into selected areas that would make the most impact for our visitors and audience members. We wanted first impressions to be positive impressions, so we partnered with Tohono O'odham artist Michael Chiago to repaint the mural on the 4-meter-diameter concrete "donut" in the visitor parking

The new Visitor Center entry wall, floor, front desk, and signage (Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/D. Salman)

lot. A new exterior sign was designed and placed near the Visitor Center entrance, and the wall immediately inside the entrance was replaced with a very large mural comprised of nighttime views of Kitt Peak. We completely rebuilt the admissions and gift shop area, doubled the number of cash registers to speed up check-in lines, replaced all the slat walls throughout the gift shop, and redesigned the check-in desk. We installed a PA and microphone system to make it easier for audience members to clearly hear our daytime and evening presentations.

A large new exhibit was designed and installed, introducing guests to the importance of maintaining dark skies everywhere. Several exhibits were installed describing Kitt Peak's role in training NASA astronauts during the Apollo program. The classroom in our Roll Off Roof observatory, which is heavily used by our nighttime programs and astrophotography workshop participants, received modern IT, power, monitors, computers, and Blu-ray players en-

abling far more dynamic presentations by staff than previously possible.

A popular activity for Kitt Peak visitors has been the safe viewing of the Sun through specially designed telescopes during daytime hours. Visitors were previously required to walk a quarter of a mile in each direction to reach the small dome on the mountaintop housing these three special telescopes. For mobility-challenged and elderly guests, this represented a barrier. With some ingenious engineering work by one of our docents, we redeveloped a storage shed located only 80 feet from the Visitor Center entrance into a unique split-function observatory. The south room within this building now houses the three solar telescopes, and the north room houses a donated 12.5-inch imaging telescope to support our popular Overnight Telescope Observing Programs. We call this repurposed building SOLARIO, for SOLAR & Imaging Observatory.

Five new outdoor exhibits were designed and installed.

New outdoor exhibits located at the western overlook where the sunset viewing portion of our nighttime programs occurs (Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/W. Buckingham)

Relatively near to the Visitor Center, the first exhibit introduces our audiences to the WIYN 3.5m Telescope. Located farther up a small hill, the second exhibit describes the SARA-North Telescope. The other three exhibits provide an introduction to radio astronomy, identify all the observatories on the southwest ridge, and discuss why the daytime sky is blue and sunsets are red. The pathway that all five exhibits are located along is the most heavily utilized pedestrian pathway at the observatory.

While all these improvements were being designed, constructed, and installed, we developed the plan to preserve the McMath-Pierce Solar Telescope after its retirement by the National Solar Observatory at the end of December 2017. Originally built in 1962 as the world's largest solar observatory, the McMath-Pierce remains in solid shape and has a number of rooms and areas that ceased to be actively used well before its formal retirement. Most of these areas lie underground and include former photographic dark rooms, a large machine shop, electronics and optical shops, photographic plate storage, and offices. It was the realization that nearly all of these spaces were no longer being used by the few researchers still observing with the McMath-Pierce that was the driver behind the Visitor Center-developed concept to convert the facility into a

world-class astronomy outreach center. The National Science Foundation is the major funder of this initiative.

Although most of the rooms are too small to function in this new role, when common interior walls are removed during major reconstruction starting later this year, we will gain areas large enough for a planetarium, several immersive exhibits areas, and a Science On a Sphere theater. We plan to continue operating the three large solar telescopes, or heliostats, located atop the facility to provide both daytime and evening celestial viewing for visitors.

Once completed, the new facility within the McMath-Pierce will be known as Windows on the Universe Center for Astronomy Outreach. This represents the next big leap for the Kitt Peak Visitor Center in its capacity to welcome, engage, and provide enjoyable learning experiences for visitors. It will enable us to broaden our story to include the work and discoveries from ground-based telescopes around the world now operated or being developed by the National Science Foundation. Visitors will learn a more comprehensive story of modern astronomy than we can presently provide. We will also have the capability to create and share dynamic astronomy images and visualizations with hundreds of museums, bringing the excitement of modern astronomy to entirely new audiences.

Visitor Center docents and staff familiarize themselves with the new SOLARIO facility (Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/D. Salman)

The August Milky Way arches over the McMath-Pierce solar observatory (Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/D. Salman)